

FUTURE MIGRATION
SCENARIOS FOR EUROPE

Report

SLOVENIA

Migration and demographic patterns in Central-Eastern Europe

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Report

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Abstract

This report is a part of deliverable "D.6.2. Report on migration and demographic patterns in the EU CEE countries and potential source countries" from the project FUME – Future Migration Scenarios for Europe (870649), financed with the Horizon 2020 programme. In particular, this country report focuses on critical analysis of migration data from Slovenia, and in particular - immigration data. The analysis consists of an overview of stock and flow data on migrants including such dimensions as age groups, gender, country of origin, types of permits and length of residence. This report is a first step in analytical task which aims to determine migration potential from and to Slovenia and furthermore, to provide necessary data input for fine-tuning of FUME migration projection model.

Slovenia is a post-communist country with a long history of emigration and a relatively new waves of immigration from both within and outside of Europe. Prior to the declaration of independence from Yugoslavia in 1991, the country's migration trends resembled to a large extent those of other Southern and South-European states. Mainly economically-driven, but also in many periods also politically, Slovene emigrants used to leave their ethnic lands since the mid-nineteenth century and settled abroad - mostly in Western Europe but also overseas, in North and South America, Australia and many other countries. In 1980s, when Slovenia was already also an immigrant country, emigration trends slowed down until 2004, when the accession to the European Union open new pathways and opportunities for potential migrants. Contemporary Slovenia is among the few countries in the region with an increase in population when compared to the period when the communist era ended in Europe. That demographic increase, observed especially after 2017, is largely attributed to immigrants who come to Slovenia mostly for work, but also for family reasons and education. Most of immigrants come from the countries of former Yugoslavia.

This report presents the historical framework of migration transformation in Slovenia, diaspora dynamics and major national groups of immigrants and their demographic structure. It also provides critical analysis of the validity of the main statistical data sources, and suggests migration scenarios for the future.

1. Introduction

Mass emigration of Slovenians dates back to the nineteenth century, when the country was part of the Austro-Hungarian empire. With the exception of missionaries and soldiers, it had predominantly economic and overseas character (Medved 2014: 154). The most popular destination at that time was the United States of America and it had two early phases: 1) the pioneer period with Slovene missionaries, 2) mass migration 1880-1924 (Klemencic 1986). Other Slovenians went to Argentina, Brazil, Egypt, Belgium and other European countries at the higher level of development. Until the First World War around 300,000 Slovenians left their land and settled abroad, which was, as it is estimated, above 20% of the population. The exact numbers are, however, unknown, since Slovenians emigrated as citizens of other countries, first Austro-Hungarian then Yugoslavia and the available archive data often does not include information on ethnic origin of newcomers. In the 1920s, the political motive, namely the Fascist policies towards the Slovene minority, also became an important push factor which led to a significant wave of emigration to Yugoslavia or further, among others to Argentina. Besides, the economic crisis of the 1930s contributed to the next wave of mass economic migration. There are estimations that prior to World War II up to 100,000 people living in Yugoslavia, but outside of Slovenia identified themselves as Slovencs (Žigon 1993 as cited in Vah Jevšnik and Cukut Krilić, 2020: 442; Žigon 2004: 26).

Next crucial migration movements happened after the World War II, when former political refugees returned to Slovenia. On the other hand, Slovenians still continued to leave the country for economic reasons and political reasons, e.g., there was an emigration wave of opponents to the communist system who moved to Argentina. Australia also became a new host country for Slovenians, but also Canada and USA continued to host new migrants. The period of 1960s to 1980s was marked by another surge in economic, but also political, emigration. Slovenians emigrated to Western European countries, such as West Germany, France and Sweden, for better job opportunities, wages and refuge. At that time Slovenia became also a destination country for people from other nations of former Yugoslavia. Between 1975 and 1982 almost 100,000 migrants came to Slovenia. The majority of them acquired later Slovenian citizenship (Drnovšek 2009, as cited in Lazarević 2019: 28; Medved 2014: 153-154; Žigon, 2004: 26).

Another turning point in the Slovenian migration history was the declaration of independence from Yugoslavia in 1991. The rate of emigration generally decreased, and the pattern reversed after 2004 with the European Union accession, which was part of a wider trend of post-accession emigration from CEE countries which had a variety of consequences for both sending and receiving countries. Then, international migration intensified again with the 2008 economic crisis. In 2007, the country joined the Schengen area, and currently its border with Croatia is the external Schengen border.

Interestingly, in Slovenia there has been an increase in the population size, which is not resembling the patterns observed generally in Central and Eastern Europe of the demographic decline. The population of Slovenia on January 1, 2021 was officially 2,108 997 thousand which was 0.6% more than a year ago and slightly higher than at independence in 1991. While in the period of 2010 – 2017 there was generally a balance between the number of emigrants and immigrants, since 2018, with the economic growth, net migration has also increased. While ageing processes are evident in Slovenia like in many parts of Europe, and the fertility rates are below the 2.1 replacement-level fertility, they are 'compensated' by immigration. While during 2020, the number of Slovenian citizens increased only by 800, the number of foreigner citizenship holders increased by more than 12 thousand. Among immigrants, there is a significant overrepresentation of men (OECD 2021, Razpotnik 2021). In 2019, Slovenia ranked 4th among European Union countries in the number of first residence permits issued to non-EU citizens per 1,000 people (Kebe, 2020). Currently, according to the Slovenian Statistical Office the share of foreigners is estimated at 8% of the total population (SORS, 2021), but in OECD assessment it is even 13,5% (OECD, 2021). Since immigration has been on the rise, the government adopted in 2019 the Strategy in the Field of Migration, which is the first such a comprehensive document in the field of migration. It is also important to stress that Slovenia is a transit country for numerous migrants trying to reach Western Europe. To prevent illegal migration, it has therefore strengthened border surveillance.

The structure of the report is as follows: at first, we present the methodological approach for the study, present the key terms and definitions used by the Slovenian public institutions in the field of migration, and provide an overview of the statistical sources on immigration statistics in Slovenia. In the second part, we present official data on immigration stock in the country along with descriptive and critical analyses. Additionally, comments on the reliability and usefulness of data are added. Finally, the report ends with conclusions and key findings, discuss the limits of official statistical registers and show areas which can be further explored.

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2. Methodology, Definitions and Sources

Methodological approach

This report is based upon desk research, and a descriptive and critical data analysis. In the first stage of the research, the team gathered the main relevant data on emigration and immigration numbers (stock and flows) from official sources in Slovenia and some other Central and Eastern European countries belonging to the EU. Data were obtained mainly from the Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia and Eurostat, as well as reports and surveys on recent migration processes related to the analyzed country. Relevant academic literature and policy papers have also been consulted. The main theme of interest and analysis was immigration, but an overview of emigration process and a discussion of the diaspora have also been included. The research team has therefore paid special attention to existing and available data on immigrant stocks and flows. The report provides a critical assessment of those data suggesting biases and problems in data collection and reliability. The migration statistics provided by the official Slovenian sources was finally compared with the estimations on immigrant flows by Abel & Cohen (2019).

Evidencing of migrants in statistical registers and definitions of migrants

In Slovenia, numerous migration-related data sources exist. They include both registers, administrative sources, and other statistical data bases. The most comprehensive database for migration statistics is held by the Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia. It gathers data from the Central Population Register (CPR) of the Ministry of the Interior, specifically data from the survey 'Migrations', and complements them with information from many other registers (SORS 2021b; Stropnik et al., 2014). The official registers include data on migration flow, immigrant/emigrant stock, acquisition of citizenship, return migration and asylum seekers (Stropnik et al. 2014: 5). Those sources cover many variables related to migrant's status, such as the official stay and residency in the country, participation in labour market, education situation (e.g., enrolment in educational institutions), demographic, economic and social features. There is information on particular categories of immigrants including their countries of birth, citizenship and stay abroad. All those sources and data bases on migration are being developed and enlarged (Stropnik et al., 2014: 39). So far, the most comprehensive and detailed register of migrants and their characteristic comes from the 2011 Census, for which statistical survey data were gathered along with other available data sources. It was the first data collection which included data on first residence of immigrants, their parents, and grandparents (Stropnik et al., 2014: 7).

Another key data source which provides information on seasonal migration is the Employment Service of Slovenia. Its register contains data on work permits obtained by foreigners. It does not, however, provide a full picture of this phenomenon, because not all categories of migrant workers are obliged to have a work permit (Stropnik et al., 2014: 39).

Regarding emigration from Slovenia, the data on emigration stock are not reliable. They include only those people who have deregistered their residence in Slovenia and moved to another country. It is thus difficult to estimate the real number of Slovenian citizens living outside of their home country (Stropnik et al., 2014). Data on international migration collected by the Statistical Office are not comparable in 100% percent due to differences in methodologies and definitions in particular periods. Prior to 1992, citizens of all Yugoslavia republics who (de)registered their permanent residence in Slovenia were included in international migration statistics. That changed in 1992, when only those migrants who possessed Slovenian citizenship and

changed their permanent residence were counted. Migrants from former Yugoslavia, who did not obtain that citizenship were treated as foreigners. That year the Ministry of the Interior deleted 18,305 people who had not obtained legal rights to stay from the database of permanent residents. Some of those people emigrated, some became illegal (SIStat 2021b; Toplak et al. 2010: 3).

Another change in the methodological approach took place in 1996, and new datasets included not only migration of Slovenian citizens, both immigration and emigration, but also foreigners. Since 1999 Slovenian statistics included not only permanent migrants, but also temporary movements (defined as exceeding 3 months) of people with Slovenian citizenship. After 2008 internal migration data covers not only people holding the citizenship of Slovenia, w bibliografii jest SORS 2021b, czy o to źródło chodzi?but also foreign citizens (SIStat 2021b).

The definitions used by the SIStat are as follows (2021b):

Residents: "A resident of Slovenia is a person, regardless of citizenship, with registered permanent and/or temporary residence in Slovenia, who has actually stayed or intends to stay in the country for one year or more and has not been temporarily absent from the country for one year or more. This means they have usual residence in Slovenia."

Immigrants: "An immigrant from abroad is a usual resident of Slovenia who has immigrated to Slovenia from abroad and has usual residence in Slovenia (intends to stay in the country for a year or more)"

Emigrants: "An emigrant from Slovenia is a usual resident of Slovenia who has emigrated abroad from Slovenia, and has a new usual residence abroad (they intend to stay abroad for a year or more)"

As in other European countries, Slovenia distinguished requirements for prospective immigrants. A relatively straightforward way to enter Slovenia relates to migrants possessing citizenship of a country belonging to the European Economic Area (EEA), who do not require a visa or a residence permit. Such documents are necessary for third country nationals (Ministry of the Interior, 2021). In the last couple of years, the Slovenian government has implemented several measures to simplify and speed the procedures for work and residence permits for some groups of foreigners. Moreover, since 2018 Croatian citizens can be employed by a Slovenian company without having to apply for a work permit (OECD 2020: 234).

Another channel for entering Slovenia is the international protection or asylum which can be granted to people who fulfill the criteria according to the Geneva Convention, which Slovenia has signed (Ministry of the Interior, 2021). In March 2021, amendments to the International Protection Act (IPA) were approved which introduced measures to make asylum procedures faster but also to limit violation of rules in regard to this area (OECD 2021: 304).

The family reunification process has also been subject to debates and changes. According to the new Foreigners Act from 2020, third-country nationals, with some exceptions, must first reside legally for a period of two years in Slovenia in order to be eligible to apply for their families' residence permits (Ibidem).

Picture: Kenzie De Schepper/Unsplash.com

3.Slovenian diaspora

The Slovenian concept “Slovensko zamejstvo” (Medved 2014: 153) refers to regions outside of the country where Slovene minorities dwell and, in particular, to four neighboring states: Italy, Austria, Hungary, and Croatia. Italy has the largest Slovenian population, but it is impossible to obtain reliable data, as they are not counted in an official way. In 2014, the Slovenian Government Office for Slovenians Abroad estimated that the number may be realistically around 70,000 and 80,000 of people. In Austria, mostly in Carinthia region and along the border, there can be between 20,000 or 30,000 members of the Slovenian community. Hungary is a host country for a tiny Slovenian minority, which is estimated to equal about 3,000. There is also a community of around 3,500 in Croatia (Medved 2014: 153-4).

Slovenian diaspora is also present overseas, in the countries which attracted Slovenes during mass migration in various periods since the mid-nineteenth century. Most of them live in the United States, Canada, Argentina, or Australia. According to the Government’s Office for Slovenians Abroad, nowadays there are up to 500,000

of Slovenian emigrants and their descendants living abroad but only 160,000 are still citizens of Slovenia. There is, however, no up-to-date information on the diaspora situation, since the Statistical Office of Slovenia does not collect such data. The only official available data come from the Population Register of the Ministry of Interior (Vah Jevšnik, Cukut Krilić 2020: 443). OECD (2021) estimates that the largest groups of Slovenes living in the OECD countries are in Germany, Austria, and Switzerland.

From the perspective of migration processes it is important to underline the preferential measures which the country grants to Slovenian emigrants or people with Slovenian roots, who do not hold Slovenian citizenship, but are interested in obtaining it. Those potential returnees can take advantage of a variety of policy tools, such as preferential employment tools or access to higher education (Vah Jevšnik, Cukut Krilić 2020: 441).

Figure 1. Recent emigration from Slovenia.

Source: SORS 2021.

Official data on the scale of emigration is the emigrant stock provided by the Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia (SORS) in the statistical yearbooks. These data include only those Slovenian citizens who deregistered their residence from their home country and registered officially in another place. The main data source on emigration for SORS is thus the information obtained from other countries' registers of foreigners. Recent data are presented in Figure 1. They show a relative stability in emigration as the number of official emigrants oscillates around 15,000.

Picture: Aljaz Kavcic/Unsplash.com

4. Immigrant stock in Slovenia

Slovenia is a country characterized by a relatively high share of foreign citizens residing on its territory in comparison to other Eastern and Southern European countries. It is on the one hand due to historical processes and the consequences of the breakup of Yugoslavia and the continuous immigration from the other republics. The census data shows clearly that the majority of immigrants dwelling in Slovenia came from the territory of former Yugoslavia. On the other hand, however, currently intensifying immigration processes are mainly caused by labour demands in many sectors of the economy (Ladić, M., Bajt, V., & Jalušič, 2020).

Indeed, the immigrant stock is increasing in Slovenia and in the following part of the report, we will present the most relevant data characterizing the immigrant population in Slovenia.

Census 2011 data

According to Census 2011 results, there were 228 588 residents of Slovenia born in a foreign country, what amounted to 11,1% of the whole population (SORS, 2011). There was an increase observed since the previous Census in 2002, when immigrants constituted 8,6% of the whole Slovenian population. The Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia identified several reasons for that increase, such as the economic prosperity propelling increased labour demand, (e.g., in construction industry), accession of Slovenia to European Union in 2004 and immigrants coming from other member states, and also, family reunion that drives secondary migration of family members of foreigners already living in Slovenia (SORS, 2011).

It is estimated that 86,7% of the foreign-born residents of Slovenia originated from former Yugoslav countries, and, in general, 97,8% of immigrants living in Slovenia came from European countries, both European Union member states and countries outside of it (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Countries/regions of first residence of foreigners residing in Slovenia, 2011.
Source: SORS (2020b).

Most of foreign-born residents of Slovenia originated from Bosnia and Herzegovina (96 897 – 42,39% of the whole immigrant population), Croatia (49 158 – 21,51%), Serbia (26368 – 11,54%), North Macedonia (13 658 – 5,97%) and Kosovo (9350 – 4,09%). Montenegro, as one of the former Yugoslav republics, was also a country of origin of foreigners living in Slovenia but the group of Montenegrin immigrants was not so numerous in 2011. There were only 2811 persons of this origin residing officially in Slovenia, which amounted to 1,23% of the whole immigrant population. Foreigners born in Germany also constituted a relatively numerous group of immigrants residing in Slovenia – there were 8480 of them (3,71% of whole immigrant group) in 2011.

Figure 3. Countries of origin of the most numerous groups of foreigners residing in Slovenia, 2011.

Source: SORS (2020b).

Regarding gender aspect, almost all of the most numerous immigrant groups were predominantly masculinized in 2011. Kosovo-born population residing in Slovenia was the one characterized by the highest share of men – 71,7% of immigrants were male, followed by North Macedonia (62,7% of men) and Bosnia and Herzegovina (62,2% of men). Only Croatia-born immigrant group was slightly feminized with 50,9% share of females.

As underlined by Slovenian Statistical Office, Croatian immigrants were in average 55,7 years old, which is 14 years older than total Slovenian population. It distinguishes that group from other foreign-born residents (e.g., Kosovo-born migrants were 34,3 years old and the ones coming from North Macedonia were 39,4 years old) (SORS, 2011).

There was also a high share of Slovenian citizenship holders among foreigners in 2011. It remained relatively high even though there was a decrease observed between 2002 and 2011 Censuses, concerning the share of foreign-born population holding Slovenian citizenship. In 2002, 80% of residents born in a foreign country were Slovenian citizens, and in 2011 - 65% of them wielded Slovenian citizenship. The decrease is ascribed to increasing economic immigration preceding the 2011 Census (and consequently, rising number of temporary residence permits based on work permits) and demanding conditions for acquiring Slovenian citizenship (SORS, 2011).

National statistical database

The share of foreign-born population has been steadily increasing in Slovenia - from 11,1% in 2011 to 11,5% in 2015 and 12,1% in 2018. In numerical measures, it means that the immigrant stock in Slovenia grew by 9 028 persons in the period between 2011 and 2015, and by 12 610 from 2015 to 2018 (SORS 2020a).

According to 2018 data, most of the immigrants living in Slovenia, arrived in the country in the last three decades, with the majority coming after 2000. It is also important to stress that a large group of foreign-born inhabitants of Slovenia arrived in the years 1971-1980, meaning that they have settled in the country over 40 years ago.

It is crucial to underline that this kind of data depicts immigrant population in 2018 only. It does not concern immigrant flows from the years regarded- it rather depicts one feature of the foreign-born population living in Slovenia (length of stay).

Figure 4. Foreign-born population by year of immigration, 2018.

Source: SORS (2020b).

Most of the long-term residents who arrived in the 1970s, originate from (now former) republics of Yugoslavia, especially from Bosnia and Herzegovina (22 799 persons), Croatia (11 011) and Serbia (5396).

Concerning the 'new' immigrants – those who arrived in Slovenia after 2011, former Yugoslav republics remain the main countries of origin with Bosnia and Herzegovina being the leader (22 647 of people born there lived in Slovenia in 2018). Kosovo-born foreigners who arrived in Slovenia after 2011 were the second largest group (6 770 persons), followed by immigrants originating from Serbia (6 689 persons) and North Macedonia (5 633 persons) (SORS, 2020b).

Slovenian Statistical Office's most current data concerning immigrant stock refers to 2018, indicating that there was a population of immigrants numbering 250 226 people. The biggest national groups among them were those originating from former Yugoslav countries (notably Bosnia and Herzegovina), and some EU countries (like Germany or Italy) (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Most numerous immigrant groups by country of origin, share of whole immigrant population, 2018.

Source: SORS (2020b).

Bosnian immigrant stock, being the largest one in Slovenia (concerning country of origin), is the only one whose number exceeds 100 thousand people. Second biggest national group consists of Croatians (44 994 persons), and the third one comprises immigrants originating from Serbia (25 372) (Figure 6).

Figure 6. The most numerous immigrant groups by countries of origin and sex, 2018.

Source: SORS (2020b).

The whole immigrant population according to 2018 data was mostly masculinized – the share of men amounted to 56,6%. Concerning particular countries and categories of countries (the most numerous ones), the group of immigrants originating from former Yugoslav states was characterized by a higher masculinization rate than whole immigrant population (60,2%). Populations of immigrants coming from Bosnia and Herzegovina and Kosovo were highly masculinized (60,9% and 60,2% respectively) in 2018. A group of immigrants worth mentioning in terms of high masculinization is the one consisting of persons coming from African countries, regardless of relatively low number (822 immigrants in 2018). The share of men amounted to 69,1% in 2018.

On the other hand, the groups of immigrants originating from European Union member states and other European countries were feminized. The share of women in those large groups amounted to 50,4% and 60,8% respectively. Immigrant stock from Croatia, which is a particular case, being both a former Yugoslav country and a current EU member state, is also slightly feminized with 51,2% of women in 2018.

Table 1. Masculinization rates of immigrant population by countries or categories of countries, 2018.
Source: SORS (2020b).

	total	men	share of men
ALL	250 226	141 577	56,6%
Bosnia and Herzegovina	107 677	65 526	60,9%
Croatia	44 994	21 971	48,8%
Serbia	25 372	14 995	59,1%
North Macedonia	17 128	10 048	58,7%
Kosovo	17 051	10 263	60,2%
Germany	7 254	3 672	50,6%
Italy	4 136	2 444	59,1%
Montenegro	3 344	1 793	53,6%
former Yugoslav countries	170 572	102 625	60,2%
EU countries	65 808	32 641	49,6%
other European countries	7 144	2 801	39,2%

Concerning the age of the immigrant population, there is very limited information available in the database of the Slovenian Statistical Office. It does not allow analyzing the age of immigrants from particular countries but lets to examine foreign-born population by age groups. Comparing this information with the data about the age groups of native-born population, it is clear that age structures of those two groups vary significantly. Figure 7 pictures the age structure of the foreign-born population and indicates that more than half (50,2%) of it consists of people whose age exceeds 50 years. The same age group in the nativeborn population constitutes a share of 39,9% of the whole group (Figure 8). The largest age group among foreign-born residents of Slovenia is the one consisting of people aged 50-59 years (21,4%) while the largest one in the native-born population comprises persons aged 40-49 years (14,1%). It is worth noting, however, that the sizes of age groups in the native-born population do not vary as much as in the foreign-born population. For instance, groups of people aged 30-39, 40-49, 50-59, and 70+ years all constitute similar shares of the whole population (around 14%).

Figure 7. Age groups in the foreign-born population, 2018.
Source: SORS (2020a).

Figure 8. Age groups in the native-born population, 2018.
Source: SORS (2020a).

The recent increase in immigration is also reflected in the number of valid permits. In the statistical databases residence permits refer to third-country nationals, i.e., non-EU citizens and entitles them to stay legally on the territory of Slovenia. Residence permits concerned the numbers of all valid documents have been increasing every year. The number of all valid documents of this type grew by 57 430 between 2016 and 2020.

Table 2. All valid residence permits, as for 31st December, 2016-2020.
Source: Eurostat (2021).

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Total	109 981	123 176	145 366	164 266	167 411

The reasons for issuing the permits were mostly (apart from 'other' reasons) linked with employment. The number of permits issued on these grounds has been growing systematically until 2019, with a slight drop in 2020 most probably due to pandemic restrictions. The second most frequent reason was family (including accompanying family), and the third – education. The number of residence permits issued on these bases was steadily rising between the years 2016-2020. In particular in the years of faster economic growth – such as in 2018 and 2019 - the increase in the number of foreign workers is visible. In 2019, Slovenia ranked 4th among European Union countries in terms of first residence permits granted to foreigners counted per 1,000 population. Higher share was observed only in Malta, Cyprus, and Poland (SORS 2020, Special release).

Figure 9. All valid residence permits by reason, as for 31st December, 2016-2020.
Source: Eurostat (2021).

Picture: Miha Rekar/Unsplash.com

5. Immigrant flows in Slovenia

Even though Slovenia keeps track of the migration movements quite meticulously, it is impossible to assess the whole scale of immigrant flows due to not necessarily registered movement of citizens of the European Union, especially those staying in the country for a relatively short term. Moreover, not all types of available data pictures migration flows precisely enough, e.g., most of the available statistics do not allow analyzing migrant groups by their country of origin (differentiating only between Slovenian citizens and foreigners).

Regardless of the abovementioned, the existing data allows outlining immigrant flows in Slovenia to some extent, and our aim in this chapter is the assessment of changes in migrations to Slovenia in the last few years. By doing so, we will build a foundation for creating a further narrative scenario for migrations in the country.

What is necessary to acknowledge, Slovenian statistics regarding immigration include Slovenian citizens who constitute a considerable share of all the individuals arriving from abroad (Table 3).

Table 3. Share of Slovenian citizens among all the immigrants, 2010-2020.
Source: SORS (2022).

	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Total	15 416	14 083	15 022	13 871	13 846	15 420	16 623	18 808	28 455	31 319	36 110
Slovenia	2 711	3 318	2 741	2 250	2 535	2 755	2 863	3 288	4 354	3 759	11 360
% of Slovenians	17,6%	23,6%	18,2%	16,2%	18,3%	17,9%	17,2%	17,5%	15,3%	12,0%	31,5%

Immigration and emigration were at similar levels until 2018 when the immigration skyrocketed, rising also the net migration to almost 15 thousand which was almost 12 times higher than in the year preceding (Figure 10).

The number of immigrants choosing Slovenia as their destination country has been raising, amounting to 36110 persons in 2020 which was over 2,3 times more than a decade before.

Figure 10. Immigration, emigration and net migration to Slovenia, 2010-2020.
Source: SORS (2022).

The reason for this rapid growth of the immigration was, among others, a significantly increasing number of Bosnians arriving to Slovenia – almost two times more citizens of this country migrated in 2018, compared to 2017 (11716 compared to 6185). Similarly, the numbers of Kosovars and Serbians increased by 1,8 and 1,6 times respectively.

Bosnia and Herzegovina has been the main country of origin of immigrants arriving in Slovenia. The share of Bosnians among all the immigrants amounted to 44% in 2019, it however dropped slightly in 2020, probably due to the coronavirus pandemic effect (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Share of citizens of Bosnia and Herzegovina among all the immigrants arriving in Slovenia, 2018-2020.
Source: SORS (2022).

The feminization rate of the immigrant flows has been steadily rising over the years. In 2018, the share of women in the whole immigrant group amounted to 29,4%, with a slight drop in 2019 to 28,3%, and with an increase up to 35,9% in 2020 (SORS, 2022).

The least feminized immigrant groups in years 2018, 2019 and 2020 among the most numerous ones were those consisting of Serbians, Kosovars, Bulgarians and Bosnians. The feminization rate was oscillating between around 18% and 27%, depending on the year and the country of origin. What is worth noting, though, is the fact that the share of women has been increasing steadily in all the immigrant groups over the years.

The most feminized groups of immigrants arriving in Slovenia between 2018 and 2020 comprised of Russians, Slovenians, Macedonians and Croatians (joining the list of the most numerous immigrant groups only in 2020). The only immigrant group whose feminization rate exceeded 50% was the one consisting of Russian Federation citizens – the share of women amounted to 54,9% in 2019 and 54,1% in 2020 (Figure 12, 13, 14).

Figure 12. Share of women in the most numerous immigrant groups, by country of citizenship, 2018.

Source: SORS (2022).

Figure 13. Share of women in the most numerous immigrant groups, by country of citizenship, 2019.

Source: SORS (2022).

Figure 14. Share of women in the most numerous immigrant groups, by country of citizenship, 2020.
Source: SORS (2022).

The ranking of the most numerous immigrant groups based on their country of origin has been changing in the last few years, with significant shifts in 2020. Even though citizens of Bosnia and Herzegovina were the largest immigrant group in the years preceding, it was superseded by the number of Slovenian return migrants who constituted the most numerous immigrant group in 2020. Also, Kosovo switched places with Serbia in 2020, and interestingly, Italy appeared among the countries of citizenship of the largest immigrant groups in the place of Bulgaria. 2020, due to the pandemic, appears to be quite exceptional, therefore it might not be a proper basis for future migration diagnoses.

Concerning the immigrant group age structure, the statistics indicate that they tended to rejuvenate the Slovene population. The mean age of immigrants with foreign citizenship equaled 31,7 years in 2018, 31,2 in 2019 and 31,1 in 2020 (SORS, 2021c), while the whole population was respectively: 43,2, 43,4 and 43,5 years old on average (SORS, 2022a). The largest groups of immigrants in 2020 consisted of people aged 20-24, 25-29 and 30-34 years (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Immigrants with non-Slovene citizenship, by age groups and sex, 2020.
Source: SORS (2021c).

The largest share of immigrants aged 15 or more was characterized by upper secondary education level in all the years between 2018 and 2020. In 2020, however, the share of immigrants with tertiary education increased compared to previous years. Nonetheless, it cannot be interpreted as a trend, since 2020 seems to be an extraordinary year in terms of migration processes (Table 4).

Table 4. Immigrants aged 15 or more by education level, 2018-2020.

Source: SORS (2021).

	2018		2019		2020	
Total	25 395	100%	28 123	100%	32 188	100%
Basic or less	6 389	25,2%	7 783	27,7%	8 625	26,8%
Upper secondary	15 716	61,9%	17 270	61,4%	17 828	55,4%
Tertiary	3 290	13,0%	3 070	10,9%	5 735	17,8%

Abel and Cohen's estimates

One of our report's aims is to compare Abel and Cohen's estimates of bilateral international migration flows (2019) with statistics collected by national Slovenian institutions. Abel and Cohen's estimations are based on the dataset prepared by the United Nations Population Division (UNCPD) referring to the period between 2011 and 2015. According to their calculations, the immigrant flow for Slovenia amounted to approximately 67,2 thousand with main groups consisting of Bosnians (29596), Croatians (16094), Serbians (6008), Macedonians (4122) and Germans (3533) (Abel & Cohen, 2019).

Compared to the data provided by SORS, Abel and Cohen's estimates seem to be largely overcalculated. The total immigrant flow gauged by them is more than 7 times larger than the one calculated by us based on the SORS data. Similarly, while taking into consideration statistics referring to citizens of Bosnia and Herzegovina – their number was also overcalculated more than 7 times by Abel and Cohen. It was, however, correctly indicated as the main country of origin of immigrants arriving in Slovenia.

The rest of the most numerous immigrant groups pointed at by Abel and Cohen were indicated erroneously, compared to the national statistics. For instance, the second largest group of immigrants originated from Kosovo, according to SORS, while at the same time it was not even listed in Abel and Cohen's dataset. Moreover, countries such as Croatia and Germany were not relevant countries of origin of immigrants coming to Slovenia. In fact, according to SORS, the immigrant flow was negative for them in the period of 2011-2015 (it equaled - 2163 for Croatia and - 894 for Germany) (SORS, 2021a).

Table 5. Comparison of the data on immigration in the period of 2011-2015: Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia and Abel and Cohen's estimations.

Source: SORS (2021a), Abel & Cohen (2019).

Country of origin	SORS data	Abel and Cohen's dataset
Total	9 028	67 247
Bosnia and Herzegovina	3 983	29 596
Kosovo	2 602	-
North Macedonia	1 979	4 122
Russian Federation	962	267
Serbia	705	6 008

Taking the abovementioned into consideration, Abel and Cohen's estimates cannot be treated as a reliable tool for assessing immigration flows in Slovenia. They not only estimated the total immigrant flow in an entirely inaccurate manner but also, did not indicate the most relevant countries of origin of foreigners arriving in Slovenia. It should also be added that in the last decade the breakthrough in migration patterns in Slovenia happened after 2017. Since that year, both immigration and emigration statistics have been changing dynamically (Figure 10). 10 years ago, the migration landscape in this country did not resemble today's one, thus the data from the recent past do not provide sufficient information for forecasting the future of migration to and from Slovenia.

Picture: Ali Nuredini/Unsplash.com

6. Narrative scenario for Slovenia

In this chapter we focus on the migration potential of Slovenia as a sending and a host country, taking into account important push and pull factors such as the demographic structure, national economy, social attitudes towards foreigners, governance indicators and ecological factors. As such, these scenario narratives do not aim to foresee the migration future of Slovenia, but rather to outline the possible directions in which demographic processes can develop, also with regard to international migration.

The analysis of factors influencing the potential influx of immigrants

When it comes to demographic indicators, the Slovenian population size during the last decade has fluctuated around 2 million (Eurostat, 2021 a). It has to be mentioned that although the total fertility rate in Slovenia is gradually rising, it remains low. Between 2010 and 2015 the total fertility rate (TFR) did not exceed 1.57 and in 2019 it amounted to 1.61, which was 8 percentage points higher than the EU27 average (Eurostat, 2021 b). According to the European Commission against Racism and Intolerance (ECRI)'s report, immigration to

Slovenia has been steadily rising since 1995 and significantly increased since 2004, which is the date of the acquisition of Slovenia to the EU. In 2016 the number of foreign-born population, mainly from ex-Yugoslavian countries, totalled 5 % of all residents in Slovenia (ECRI, 2019:21).

Taking into consideration the Slovenian economy with regard to its impact on immigration, we need to note that the productivity rate is 30% lower than the average among OECD countries, which corresponds to relatively low wages – in 2020 it was 16% lower than OECD mean annual earning (OECD, 2020a). Also, we need to note that the retirement age in Slovenia is not high, as it amounts to 60 years old for both males and females, assuming the entry into the labour market at the age of 22. It reinforces the effect of a vicious circle when it comes to the unemployment rate, which in 2020 equated to 5.1 % of the labour force (OECD, 2020b).

Regarding the structure of gross domestic product in Slovenia, agriculture constituted 2% of annual GDP, industry – 29% and services – 69% in 2020. At the same time, the agricultural sector hired 4.3% of the working-age population, industry – 34.1 % and services – 61.6 % (WorldBank, 2021a; WorldBank, 2021b; WorldBank, 2021c). The analysis of the above indicators suggests that potential immigrants in Slovenia may find a job particularly in the industry and services sectors.

The significant point to discuss is the public opinion towards migration. According to the ECRI report, historically, many Slovenian minorities¹, despite their legal protection, face intolerance and prejudice from ethnic Slovenes. In recent years, Slovenian authorities paid attention to fighting discrimination and hate speech. Initiatives propagating tolerance have been introduced, such as the building the first mosque and Islamic centre in 2018 and implementing policies aiming at integrating the Roma community. However, hate speech cases are rarely prosecuted due to vague law observance by the authorities and inconsistency in the law. Moreover, legal institutions do not cooperate with each other in terms of sharing data on hate speech cases whilst showing hesitation (ECRI, 2019: 9). Therefore, potential immigrants may face acts of discrimination.

The public opinion about immigrants strictly corresponds with the use of racist and xenophobic rhetoric by politicians towards persons belonging to non-Slovene minority groups, including migrants and refugees (ECRI, 2019: 16). The unfavourable narrative has been reinforced in the state-owned media which led to the rise of Islamophobic reactions in some printed and online media, such as Novaz4tv and Demokracija during the so-called migration crisis (Ibidem).

When it comes to the environmental factors, although they are often not emphasised by many migration researchers, they are indeed significant in assessing migration movements particularly in the long-term prognoses (Dłużewski & Sobczak-Szelc, 2013: 69). Firstly, we need to mention that Slovenia is not at a high risk of climate change, compared to other region of the world. According to the climate projections, during the following thirty years, the mean temperature will not rise significantly, and the precipitation will not extremely decrease (WorldBank, 2021d). Therefore, Slovenia will most probably not be a source of climate emigration. However, importantly, the country might become a destination for climate refugees.

Migration prospect

While analysing data about immigrants from the Statistical Office in Slovenia, we need to note that the migrant groups are categorized by the continent of origin, not the country, whereof Europe is divided into three categories: European Union, countries of former Yugoslavia and other European countries. Thus, to assess the future of each immigrant group we have to operate in broad categories, which significantly diminishes the accuracy of the migration narrative scenario.

¹ Roma, Serbs, Roma, Croats, Bosniaks, Muslims, Albanians, Montenegrins and Macedonians and German speakers.

The largest group of immigrants in Slovenia came from Europe (33 thousand in 2020) and their figures were steadily rising year to year, actually doubling within a decade. The biggest subcategory of European immigrants has been born in the countries of former Yugoslavia, namely in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia and until 2016 - Croatia. Their share in 2010 amounted to 10 thousand persons, in 2015 – 8 thousand and in 2020 – 20 thousand (Statistical Office in Slovenia, 2021). Due to historical experience, linguistic and cultural proximity, we can assume that a number of this migrant network may increase.

The next biggest subcategory is citizens of the EU, whose figures in 2020 amounted to nearly 12 thousand. In the statistics appear the tendency of growing, when it comes to this migrant group, as in 2019 equated 5.3 thousand in 2015 – 4.3 thousand and in 2010 – 3.4 thousand. It must be mentioned that the peak in 2020 happened despite the pandemic, which is a manifestation of the inclusion in the labour market of migrants from EU countries. Parallely with the number of EU citizens in Slovenia increased, the size of migrants from other European countries also raised, the number still remains small, though. For instance, in 2010 it equated to ca. 570 persons, in 2015 – 1200, and in 2020 – 1500. Taking into account the tendency of growth of the migrant networks aforementioned, we can presume that the size of the group of European migrants may enlarge in the following three decades.

Although migrants from Europe undoubtedly constitute the largest share of all migrants in Slovenia, we may not miss immigrants from other continents. The next-biggest network in Slovenia consists of Asian-origin newcomers. Their number in 2010 amounted to ca. 360 persons, in 2015 – 450, and five years later – 1050. Although we cannot provide detailed information about the origin of this group, considering the traits of Asian migrants as entrepreneurial and easily-adaptive to the new culture and environment, we can assume that this migrant community may grow in the next thirty years.

We should also mention migrants from Central and North America in Slovenia, whose size is unequivocally growing as in 2010 it totalled 320 persons, in 2015 – 300 and in 2020 – 670 persons. Considering the fact that a number of these networks rose at least double, despite the Covid-19 pandemic, we may assume that this group consists of highly-qualified migrants hired as employees in international companies. Therefore, we may presume that figures of immigrants from Northern and Central America might increase.

7. Conclusions

The aim of the report was to review the main recent migration trends related to Slovenia with a particular emphasis on immigration. Based on collected data, we can present some conclusions. The main significant change regarding demography and migration in Slovenia is the shift from an emigration country into an immigration one. Recently, there has been a steady increase in the share of foreign-born population which compensates for the low fertility rates and fills the gaps in the labour market. Therefore, the current immigration is largely an economic one. Major changes have taken place since 2018 with a surge of immigrants. The development of the country's economy fostered employment opportunities. To respond to the market's needs, the government introduced measures to facilitate the employment of foreign workers.

The Covid-related restrictions have influenced mobility in Slovenia, as elsewhere in the world. However, it is yet to be seen whether the impact will be significant. For the moment, the migration statistics reveal a slight drop in the number of residence permits in 2020. That year the government adjusted procedures related to permits to the unique situation and extended the validity of many documents. On the other hand, it suspended issuing new residence documents for a certain period of time. As mobility resumed after the lockdowns, the immigration trend may continue depending to a large degree on the country's economic situation (OECD 2020). Due to the unprecedented changes brought by the global pandemics, the data for 2020 may not be useful in forecasting the future trends of immigration to Slovenia.

We have also observed an increased number of Slovenian return migrants (31,5% of all the immigrants in 2020). It is not sure, though, what is the share of ethnic Slovenes and what is the share of foreigners wielding Slovene citizenship.

Regarding the profile of immigrants in Slovenia the analyzes data reveals couple of characteristics of this group. There is a relatively low feminization levels of both immigrant stocks and flows, although it differs among various nationalities. Among the most numerous immigrant groups the most feminized are Russians, Slovenians, Macedonians and Croatians, while the least - Serbians, Kosovars, Bulgarians and Bosnians.

Immigrant stock is characterized by a higher mean age than the whole Slovenian population while immigrant flows are the opposite – they are characterized by a lower mean age than the whole population.

Former Yugoslav republics have been key countries of origin of immigrants arriving in Slovenia. It's worth to remember that the status of those countries in relation to the EU differs which has an impact on the international mobility opportunities – Slovenia and Croatia are EU members, Serbia, Montenegro and North Macedonia are official candidates for the EU membership, and Bosnia and Herzegovina and Kosovo are potential candidates (i.e., they have applied for membership, but have not been approved yet). While Bosnia and Herzegovina remains the main sending country, the share of its citizens among all immigrants in Slovenia has been decreasing.

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